

SATISFIABILITY IS IN P

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Any well-defined Boolean expression/Formula(F) with n variables, $x_1, x_2, x_3 \dots x_n$, can be converted to 3-CNF. So, F can be formally expressed as:

$$F = \bigwedge_{i=1}^m C_i,$$

where each clause, C_i ($i= 1$ to m) is $\bigvee_1^3 l_j$. Here, each literal, l_j is either x_k or $\sim x_k$. For ease of handling, we index every negation of x_k as y_{2p} , while the non-negated (or straight) Boolean variables are odd-indexed serially, y_p . Thereby, all the literals are properly indexed uniquely, ranging from 1 to $2n$ and a 3-CNF formula is made as a list of tuples, each tuple comprising three positive integers.

Algorithm for finding if F is satisfiable:

1. For each clause (i.e. tuple of three positive integers representing the indices) C_i :
Sort elements in ascending order within the clause.
2. Sort the list of tuples in lexicographical order.
3. Now, look for patterns of tuples of the form:

(x, y, z1)
(x, y, z1+1)
(x, y+1, z2)
(x, y+1, z2+1)
(x+1, y, z3)
(x+1, y, z3+1)
(x+1, y+1, z4)
(x+1, y+1, z4+1)

//Note: In the above pattern, x, y, z1, z2, z3 and z4 all must be odd and there may be intervening tuples among the above eight tuples

4. If no pattern is found in step 3, F is satisfiable; otherwise F is unsatisfiable.

Proof of correctness:

1. Sorting within a clause is permissible, as OR operation is commutative.
2. Sorting the list of clauses (i.e. tuples) is permissible, as AND operation is commutative.
3. Now, we form a theorem given below to prove the third step of the algorithm:
Let L be a list of tuples of utmost three positive integers (as per proposed indexing of literals).

Theorem: L is unsatisfiable iff the pattern of the form:

(x, y, z1)
(x, y, z1+1)
(x, y+1, z2)

$(x, y+1, z+1)$
 $(x+1, y, z)$
 $(x+1, y, z+1)$
 $(x+1, y+1, z)$
 $(x+1, y+1, z+1)$ exists in L.

Proof:

\Rightarrow : Assume L is unsatisfiable.

It implies that at least one tuple is $(0, 0, 0)$.

As one of the cases, let it be (even, even, even).

Also, let it be $(x+1, y+1, z+1)$.

It means there exists $(x, y, z) = (1, 1, 1)$, as forced by $(0, 0, 0)$.

As it is always tried to make as many tuples as possible “live” (at least one element of a tuple is 1), it is spanned to have:

$(0, 0, 1)$ (1)

$(0, 1, 0)$ (2)

$(1, 0, 0)$. (3)

Here, consider $(1, 0, 0)$.

The tuple $(1, 0, 0)$ should have been obtained forcibly by the existence of tuples with 1's in the position of y and z.

It implies there should be:

$(0, 1, 0)$

$(1, 1, 0)$

$(0, 1, 1)$, for y position. Find for z similarly.

Arguing the same way for (1) and (2) and considering distinct tuples only, we get the claimed pattern of eight tuples in L.

Similarly, the argument can be made for all other patterns like (odd, even, even).

\Leftarrow : Assume the claimed pattern of eight tuples exists in L.

Note the condition of the proposed algorithm that the first tuple of eight tuples must be (odd, odd, odd) and the other tuples toggle between odd and even regularly from z position to y position to x position.

This exactly represents 000 to 111 in the generation of binary numbers with 3 bits.

So, when the eight tuples of the pattern exist, for any assignment of truth values to the variants of x , y and z , a tuple, $(0, 0, 0)$ exists as one among the eight tuples.

Therefore, L is unsatisfiable.

Hence, the theorem.

Time Complexity:

Step 1 takes $\Theta(n^3)$ time, as ${}^{2n}C_3$ (utmost) clauses only are possible for any F , as sorting is done within clause (each clause takes constant time).

Step 2 takes time $\Theta(n^3 \log n)$ in the worst case.

Step 3 requires only index-based searches in the sorted list of tuples which take $\Theta(n^3)$ time, as ${}^{2n}C_3$ (utmost) clauses only are possible.

Summing up, the above algorithm is a polynomial-time taking algorithm.

Concluding Remark:

So, 3-CNF is in P.

Since $SAT \alpha 3-SAT$, SAT is in P.

Hence, according to Cook's Theorem, $P = NP$.